

PERSONALITY FACTOR IN THE STATE ADMINISTRATION OF AZERBAIJAN IN 1993-2003

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Abstract

After gaining independence, Azerbaijan had to solve certain basic issues, including the creation of a modern democratic state, as well as the introduction of appropriate international and domestic policies. To guarantee its independence and freedom, the country needed a strong leader capable of creating a modern state administration and protecting the national interests of the country.

The transition to a new society in Azerbaijan has a solid theoretical and scientific basis thanks to the ideas and policies of Heydar Aliyev. The practical actions and ideological and political views of Heydar Aliyev played a significant role in the self-determination of the modern statehood of the Azerbaijani people. This article looks at how national leader Heydar Aliyev built the contemporary Azerbaijan Republic's public administration and philosophy of statehood after independence. Developing the idea of national statehood in accordance with the national interests of the country and the line of state-building, Heydar Aliyev laid the foundation for the rapid growth and development of the republic.

Keywords: Public administration, Heydar Aliyev, philosophy of statehood, modernization of Azerbaijan, national interests

Introduction After the collapse of the Soviet Empire, Azerbaijan was declared an independent country. Due to the penetration and propaganda of external and internal political opponents, the security of the country was under serious threat. Developing the idea of national statehood in accordance with the national interests of the country, Heydar Aliyev laid the foundation for the current rapid growth and development of the republic. It is clear that strengthening and protecting statehood is inherently a more difficult task than establishing or restoring independence, which has been repeatedly demonstrated throughout world history. After gaining independence, Azerbaijan worked to create conditions conducive to the development of a democratic, legal and secular state. National interests and the choice of the best way of domestic and foreign policy of the state have become an urgent national need. Creating a safe environment and building a solid foundation is essential to achieve and protect national interests. All this was unattainable in the first years of independence due to the escalating problems and failures caused by the inexperienced leadership of the country. National leader Heydar Aliyev has made a significant scientific, theoretical and practical contribution to the sphere of public administration, having developed a perfect concept of statehood based on scientific principles and intellectual potential. The idea of statehood in Azerbaijan since the time of Heydar Aliyev was to provide everyone with equal access to all aspects of society.

The young Republic of Azerbaijan, having broken with the empire and the totalitarian system, faced competing and overlapping interests of regional and global powers, striving to find its place in the modern world,

and the training of Heydar Aliyev in the art of state became a real strategy of action. The philosophy of statehood, national morality and ideological and political outlook - all this plays a significant role in the theoretical legacy of Heydar Aliyev. His policy laid the theoretical and scientific basis for the modernization of Azerbaijan, abandoning the rule of violence. At the international conference on public administration reform of Azerbaijan on March 16, 1999, the great leader said: "Reforms in the public administration system of Azerbaijan have been carried out and positive results have been obtained. In connection with the implementation of economic reforms and the privatization program, more than 20 ministries, state committees, agencies and enterprises were liquidated. Some bodies in various ministries and administrative institutions were either liquidated or their activities were transformed in accordance with the needs of the market economy. Reforms are being carried out in all directions, and they must be continued. The implementation of reforms in the public administration system is of particular importance compared to other reforms."

As part of his activities in the field of public administration, Heydar Aliyev developed the national ideology "Modern Azerbaijan", which serves to unite and motivate the sovereign population of Azerbaijan. Heydar Aliyev used the unifying concept of Azerbaijanism put forward at that time and used it as a platform for the national unification of Azerbaijanis around the world, thereby preserving the principle of continuity in building a system of national and ideological beliefs.

Research aims and objectives

The aim of the research is to study the theoretical heritage of the national leader of the Azerbaijani people

Heydar Aliyev and the intellectual foundations of the modern approach of the Republic of Azerbaijan to public administration. To achieve the goal stated in the article, it is necessary to analyze the following problems:

- Study of Heydar Aliyev as the founding leader of the Azerbaijani people, and his views on statehood;
- Political and public activity of Heydar Aliyev from 1993 to 2003 served as a sufficient justification for the revival of independent Azerbaijan;
- To highlight the decrees and orders signed by Heydar Aliyev, as well as his initiative to improve the public administration of Azerbaijan

The idea, key guidelines and features of the strategy of public administration of Azerbaijan are in the focus of this study, which examines this policy within the framework of the theoretical legacy of the national leader of the Azerbaijani people, Heydar Aliyev. The study of the role of Heydar Aliyev in the development of the traditions of the statehood of the Republic of Azerbaijan allows us to consider the historical role of Heydar Aliyev in the creation and development of the public administration system of the Republic of Azerbaijan [12].

Researchers of this period [6, pp. 111-113] claim that in the 1990s, changes in the economy, government and society of Azerbaijan, as in other socialist countries, caused a number of problems for public administration. After Azerbaijan gained independence, work began on the restoration of the public administration system, improving the state apparatus and the civil service. The Decree of national Leader Heydar Aliyev "On the establishment of the Commission for Legal Reforms" in 1996 and the Decree "On the establishment of the State Commission for the Reform of Public Administration" in 1998 played a very important role in the implementation of positive changes. It was this decree that laid the foundation for the changes that led to the creation of a progressive management system.

The proposed reforms of public administration to create a professional institute of public service was also one of the most important points. One of the most important goals of changes in public administration is the improvement of the civil service, which is a special part of the Government.

The Constitution, which was approved by a vote on November 12, 1995, is a very important part of Government management. This laid the foundation for a democratic and rule-of-law State and for the first time the expression "civil service" was included in national legislation. The Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan is the most important legal document. It establishes the basic norms of law in the country and is the basis for all laws of the republic as a whole. By a decree signed by the country's leader Heydar Aliyev on December 29, 1998, a State commission was established.

1. History of Public Administration of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Independence and subsequent reforms played a decisive role in the creation of a sovereign State. Carrying out numerous cultural and economic transformations, the Azerbaijani people turn to their own moral principles, national and moral history, and the experience of democratic countries. Important features of any

real civil society are freedom of thought, speech and the press, inviolability of the individual, protection of fundamental human and freedoms. All these principles are reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan [2]. The first Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan adopted in 1995 covered all the bases, both economic and political, as well as social and humane.

Azerbaijan, like many other post-socialist countries, faced significant problems in public administration and other sectors when the political, economic and social climate changed in the 1990s [17, p. 22].

Analyzing the events of the 90s, some authors argue that this unpredictable political and economic climate required the formation of a development plan and guarantees of the country's national security. Azerbaijan's natural resources and strategic position have played a role in the country's economic growth [5, pp.77-105]. However, great credit belongs to Heydar Aliyev and the oil plan that he implemented. In 1994, the "Contract of the Century" was signed, which embodied the decision of the national leader to use the strategic resources of Azerbaijan as one of several long-term plans to ensure the economic security of the country. The adoption of new laws, adaptation of existing economic laws to the norms of Azerbaijan and other legislative measures contributed to the economic growth of our republic.

The changes implemented by our national leader Heydar Aliyev since 1993 have also affected the civil service. As a result of the work of the State Commission established under the direct leadership of Heydar Aliyev, the Law "On Public Service" was adopted [11] Three main objectives of this law have been achieved:

1. the development of clear and transparent procedures for the promotion and remuneration of civil servants;
2. guarantee of adequate training for the civil service corps; and
3. protection of civil servants from unfair dismissal.

2. Personality factor in public administration

The return of Heydar Aliyev to power in 1993 marked a turning point in the history of Azerbaijan. World experience proves that historical figures elected by the people bear great responsibility for determining and implementing the internal and foreign policy of the state. The most important decisions are made after their last word [14, pp.31-40]. Heydar Aliyev, the national leader of the Azerbaijani people, an outstanding statesman and politician, is such a historical figure. The protection, strengthening, eternity, permanence and irreversibility of the state independence of the Republic of Azerbaijan, as well as the formation of its foreign policy became possible thanks to his deep knowledge, extensive experience in public administration, skill and innate talent [10]

Since the return of Heydar Aliyev to power in 1993, the country has taken significant steps to create a rule-of-law state and a civil society based on national and universal values; the future of the country's democratic development has been determined; political con-

ditions have been created, sectoral laws have been developed, legislation has been strengthened and legal reforms have been carried out. The topic of national statehood, which has become a very serious problem over the past hundred years, was transferred from the sphere of science, theory, philosophy to the sphere of real politics and practical life as a result of the intensive and constant efforts of Heydar Aliyev [13]

The successes achieved in economic life have influenced the growth of Azerbaijan's political authority. Speaking at the 49th session of the UN General Assembly on September 29, 1994, President Heydar Aliyev informed the world community about the first steps taken by the country in the field of integration into the world economy [18].

As a result of the far-sighted policy of the President of Azerbaijan, on September 20, 1994, 11 major oil companies representing seven countries signed the "Contract of the Century". In November 1997, contracts were signed for the joint development of 8 more oil and gas fields. By that time, 20 large oil companies from 12 countries were operating in the Azerbaijani sector of the Caspian Sea [8, p.119]

In a very short time, Azerbaijan has accumulated sufficient experience in the field of creating an institutional system that formed the core of a modern democratic state. Representative bodies formed on the basis of basic democratic elections, executive power, institutionally independent judicial bodies have been created in the country, and the process of formation and optimization of local self-government bodies has begun. After the stage of formation of the institutional system of the new statehood under the leadership of President Heydar Aliyev, the process of searching for optimal forms of this system in accordance with local conditions was continued. This process has set tasks for deepening and expanding structural reforms, searching for more effective forms of organizing the process of public administration. The unification of state committees and ministries, the creation of some new ministries, such as the Ministries of Fuel and Energy, Transport, can be considered as part of this process. In general, the abolition of more than 20 administrative bodies, the creation of new ministries, committees and departments, the implementation of institutional reforms in the financial, banking, tax and insurance systems have led to positive changes in the field of public administration, in particular to the improvement of the administrative structure, the functional principle of management [1, p.23].

The adoption of the "Election Law" by the Milli Majlis was a significant step in the establishment and development of democracy in Azerbaijan. Heydar Aliyev regarded it as a very valuable law, the first democratic document in the history of the Republic of Azerbaijan [4, p. 777].

Heydar Aliyev considered the protection of human and civil rights and freedoms to be the main task. On the eve of the 50th anniversary of the UN Universal Declaration, adopted on December 10, 1948, our country carried out large-scale actions to further develop democracy and protect human rights, and educational

work was intensified. The Presidential Decree of February 22, 1998 "On measures to ensure human and civil rights and freedoms" is a vivid reflection of these actions [19, p. 12-15].

The decree signed by the President on December 29, 1998 "On the establishment of the State Commission for the Reform of the Public Administration system in the Republic of Azerbaijan" marked the beginning of serious reforms towards the formation of an effective public administration system. The reforms were supposed to be carried out in four directions: the reconstruction of the public expenditure management system, the reform of the audit system, the reform of the public administration system (administrative civil service), the reform of the legal and judicial system.

In March 1999, with the participation of experts from the Government of Azerbaijan and the World Bank, an international conference was held on the issue of reforms of the public administration system in Azerbaijan. Detailed discussions were held on the existing problems in this area, their solutions and the content of the draft concept of the expected reforms. One of the most important issues during the reforms was the restructuring of the government structure, the fundamental simplification of the management structure by switching from field principles to functional principles.

One of the most important conditions for effective management is the issue of restructuring the resource management system in the public sector. Several steps have been taken to this end. First of all, a new law on the budget system was adopted.

To ensure the effective functioning of the state and the successful solution of the upcoming problems, much depends on civil servants who are highly qualified, protected by law, value the interests of society, are worthy, cultured, know how to use modern information tools and are able to lead effectively. Proceeding from this, the formation of the institute of public service that meets the requirements of the time was considered as one of the most important issues. To this end, on July 21, 2000, the Law "On Public Service" was developed and adopted, which entered into force in September 2001. It was amended by the Laws of July 2, 2002 and December 3, 2002 [1, p.14].

The adoption of this law defined the criteria and principles of reforming the civil service in the country, created a system of certification and classification, ensuring an accurate distribution of responsibilities between different categories of civil servants and the performance of their functions, allowed to evaluate the effectiveness of civil servants and identify problems in their professional development. In addition, an opportunity was provided for the formation of a control system that ensures the promotion of employees, as well as creating conditions for highly qualified employees to remain in public service. The law defines the principles that ensure the responsibility of the civil service to society, as well as to set specific requirements for employees such as transparency, professionalism and ethics.

This law, based on world experience and conforming to international standards in many aspects, can be assessed as an important progress. The Public Service

Management Council was organized and started functioning in order to monitor the application of the law on Public Service, determine the regulatory and methodological guarantees of public service, identify persons belonging to the category of civil servants, and ensure the solution of problems related to public service in Azerbaijan as a whole.

The creation of an independent body is very important to ensure the effectiveness, transparency and objectivity of various procedures used in the process of admission to public service, promotion, certification of civil servants, their financial support and resolution of disciplinary issues. The adopted regulatory documents for the first time indicate admission to the civil service on a competitive basis, certification of civil servants, compulsory insurance, provision of additional remuneration to them, determination of qualification degrees and reflect many other important issues. Of particular note is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated August 4, 2003 "Collection of classifications of administrative and auxiliary duties", which gave impetus to the actual functioning of the law "On Public Service". With the approval of this important document, a new stage in the organization of public service has begun. The collection consists of 5 sections, here administrative and auxiliary duties and organizational problems of the civil service are defined. After the approval of the collection, there were real opportunities for improvement and reconstruction of the civil service. In March 2002, the European Union "TASIS" project on the implementation of reforms in the field of public service in Azerbaijan began to operate [16, pp.12-14], the purpose of which is:

- Development of strategy and implementation of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Public Service";
- Development of more detailed recommendations on recruitment, testing and promotion;
- Assistance in the creation of a centralized database of civil servants.

The decree of Heydar Aliyev dated January 3, 1999 on the establishment of the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan was an important step in strengthening and further development of statehood and training of thinking, modern cadres of a new generation. The national leader often said: "A person without managerial experience cannot lead the state." Therefore, he considered the creation of the Academy of Public Administration necessary.

3. Heydar Aliyev and Azerbaijanism

The philosophy of Azerbaijanism was based on the principles of multiculturalism, national tolerance and religious openness, which have long been associated with Azerbaijan. The ideology of Azerbaijanism is a concept that characterizes the ethical devotion of Azerbaijanis around the world to their native country [15]. Heydar Aliyev brought pluralism of opinions, a democratic and free style of thinking, a strong sense of social justice and a sense of national identity to Azerbaijan even during the reign of Soviet ideology.

The natural result of such a well-thought-out strategy gave its positive result and created a kind of national cadre. The progress achieved at that time helped to lay the foundation for a modern, independent Azerbaijani state. It was then that Heydar Aliyev laid the foundation for his subsequent success as one of the most prominent world leaders and statesmen, and also raised the bar of his native Azerbaijan [7; 9, 14-16].

Heydar Aliyev has always been devoted to serving his country and fatherland - Azerbaijan. He proved his competence as a leader and as a statesman. This was due to his attractive personality and extraordinary character traits. The activity of this gifted statesman was highly appreciated not only in the Soviet Union, but also beyond its borders. In the Western press, he earned the nicknames "Iron Muslim Leader of the Soviets" and "Kremlin Turk" [15].

Conclusion The founder of the Azerbaijani statehood, Heydar Aliyev was the author of global initiatives that were recognized by the entire people and respected by the international community. It must be remembered that national leader Heydar Aliyev took the helm of the state when the bipolar world collapsed. Heydar Aliyev showed a deep understanding of the state tasks facing Azerbaijan and carried out major full-scale reforms aimed at modernizing all spheres of public life. A cardinal transformation of the social system and public relations is associated with his name.

The name of Heydar Aliyev is associated not only with the salvation of the nation from a fratricidal war, but also with a difficult period of great changes that took place in the 90s. A truce reached. The neutralization of armed groups, the stabilization of the national currency, the adoption of the first national constitution, the conclusion of the largest oil contract of the century, "Election Law", first law of "On Public Service", parliamentary elections, develop democracy and protect human rights - these are just some of the results of the tireless work of Heydar Aliyev, which are not only results, but also realities taking place before our eyes. I would like to recall the capacious dictum of Heydar Aliyev "You can be in opposition to the government, but you cannot be in opposition to the Motherland, the people, morality and high ideals".

The nineties prepared a phenomenal breakthrough of the country's economy. At this stage of Azerbaijan's development, under the leadership of its leader Heydar Aliyev, it was possible to pass the post-Soviet transit in the shortest possible time and carry out fundamental structural transformations. Heydar Aliyev demonstrated perseverance, the ability to acutely raise problems and propose ways to solve them systematically, not only at the national level, but also in solving issues of international scale.

The national leader laid the practical foundations of state-building multiculturalism and the policy of social stability, interethnic harmony and moral development. The policy of national leader Heydar Aliyev has changed not only the economic structure of the country, the foundations of a new Azerbaijani mentality have been laid on the basis of values such as unity, stable development, peace and harmony.

In the course of everyday political practice, H. Aliyev directed and supported the development of forms of democratic government, the organization of political, socio-economic, cultural life, as well as the creative initiative of individuals. The strong presidential power, laid down by national leader Heydar Aliyev, guided the development of Azerbaijan, which confidently, without conflicts and social upheavals, overcame very difficult years of economic reforms. Heydar Aliyev clearly defined the real political possibilities of the country, the people, and state bodies – this was important for understanding the state, problems and prospects of national independence. The corridor of Azerbaijan's political opportunities was determined by its own historical experience, traditions, lifestyle, peculiarities of political culture and mentality.

In the American tradition, the concept of the founding fathers has become entrenched. For our people, Heydar Aliyev is, without exaggeration, the founding father of independent Azerbaijan.

References:

1. **Abdullayev V.** *Azərbaycan yeni diplomatiya məkanında.* Bakı, 2000
2. Azərbaycan Cumhuriyeti Anayasası. Hukuk Neşriyatı. Bakü, 2017
3. **Abdullayev V.** *Azərbaycan* Azərbaycan Respublikası Qanununun tətbiq edilməsi barədə Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Fərmanı (29 dekabr 2000-ci il) Əlavə və dəyişiklik: 24 avqust 2002, N775
<https://files.preslib.az/projects/stateservice/2fes.pdf> (date of access: 22.03.23.)
4. Azərbaycan. Oktyabr 94 - mart 95. Qəsd. Bakı, 1995
5. Bahram Khalilov & Afag Huseyn. Civil Service Reform in the Republic of Azerbaijan, Public Service Evolution in the 15 Post-Soviet Countries, 2022, pp 77–105
6. Bilgin, Kamil Ufuk ve Hasanov, Mürteza (2002), *Azərbaycan'da Kamu Yönetiminde Yerel Yönetimlere.* Yıl 2019, Cilt 2, Sayı 1, 111 – 133
7. Əliyev Q. *Heydər Əliyev və milli mentalitet fəlsəfəsi.* Bakı, Qismət, 2003
8. Heydər Əliyev. *Azərbaycan nefti dünya siyasətində.* Bakı, 1997
9. Huseynova L. The Issue of Genocide and Deportation of Azerbaijanis in The Focus of the State (1993-2003). *Colloquium-journal №14 (137), 2022, s.14-16*
10. İsmayılov Ə., Əliyev Q. *Heydər Əliyev və milli ləyaqət fəlsəfəsi.* Bakı, Təbib, 1998
11. Presidential Decree № 53 (29.12.1998) that came into force on 1 September 2001
12. Heydar Aliyev. <https://heydaraliyevpalace.az/en/heydar-aliyev>(date of access: 21.03.23.)
13. Kazımlı H. *Böyük siyasətin davamı.* Bakı, Nurlan, 2007
14. Менегетти А. *Психология лидера.* Москва. НБФ, 2002
15. The Milli Majlis of the Azerbaijan Republic. <https://meclis.gov.az/index.php?lang=en> (date of access: 21.03.23.)
16. Yanq R., Şabanov R. *Azərbaycanda müasir dövlət qulluğu modeli axtarışı: dünya təcrübəsi kontekstində.* TACİS layihəsi çərçivəsində. Bakı, 2004
17. Young R. and Azadov E. *Public administration reform: Achievements, challenges and perspectives.* Baku, CBS Polygraphic Production Press, 2004
18. Гусейнова И. *Гейдар Алиев– от политического руководителя к общенациональному лидеру.* Баку, 2005
19. Указы и распоряжения Президента Азербайджанской Республики (январь-март 1998 г.). Баку, 1998